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RESULTS**

ADVANCING SCIENCE EDUCATION: AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF THE SCAFFOLDED FRAMING APPROACH IN SOLO TAXONOMY ON ENHANCING STUDENT HIGHER ORDER THINKING SKILLS (HOTS) IN SCIENCE

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic caused significant learning disruptions, particularly in Science, where comprehension and higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) declined due to remote learning limitations. To address these gaps, this study examined the effectiveness of integrating the Scaffolded Framing Approach (SFA) within the Structure of the Observed Learning Outcomes (SOLO) Taxonomy among Grade 7 students at Santa Cruz Integrated National High School–Gatid Extension during the 2023–2024 school year. The Department of Education's low national results in the 2022 PISA assessment underscored the urgent need for interventions to enhance students' critical and reflective thinking.

Methods

The study employed a quantitative quasi-experimental design using a one-group pre-test and post-test approach. Forty Grade 7 students who scored below 80% in previous Science assessments were selected through stratified random sampling. The intervention covered six Science lessons during the fourth quarter of S.Y. 2023–2024. Each lesson followed a sequence: a pre-assessment to measure prior knowledge, a three-day scaffolded instruction using the framing approach, and a post-assessment to measure learning progress. Assessment tools were validated and aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) under the HOTS-SOLO framework. Data from pre- and post-tests were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and a t-test for dependent means to determine significant differences between scores.

Results

Findings showed substantial improvement in students' Science performance after the intervention. The mean pre-assessment score was 14.92 (MPS = 37.31, Low), while the post-assessment mean rose to 24.45 (MPS = 61.13, High). This indicated a positive shift in proficiency from "low" to "high." Statistical analysis revealed a t-value of 17.66, greater than the critical value of 2.023, with a p-value of 0.00001, showing a significant difference between pre- and post-test results. The improvement confirmed that the scaffolded framing approach effectively enhanced students' higher-order thinking, comprehension, and engagement in Science lessons.

Discussion

The integration of scaffolded framing within SOLO Taxonomy proved effective in improving learning outcomes and developing higher-order thinking. Structured guidance helped students navigate complex concepts, promoting independence and deeper reasoning. These results align with previous studies (Pereira & Lopes, 2021; Li et al., 2019) highlighting scaffolding's role in enhancing scientific

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reasoning and metacognitive skills. Although scores did not reach “very high” levels, the improvement reflected meaningful progress in analytical abilities.

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